

1 **T- and B-cell development and the TNF superfamily.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription during lymphocyte development of CD34+ human HSC from umbilical
8 cord blood during *in vitro* specification of T- and B-cell lymphocytes to identify developmental regulators of
9 lymphopoiesis. Differential expression of TNF and TNFR superfamily genes in the DN, SP and DP
10 lymphocyte stages alluded to a 'molecular selection pressure' generated by stage-selective expression.
11 Tnfsf13b functioned by selective repression in the CD8+ lineage. Tnfsf11 functioned instead by selective
12 induction in early T-cell progenitors (CD45+ CD7+ CD5- CD1a-) prior to specification of CD4+ and CD8+ T
13 cell types.

14 Citations

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